

Critical and Reformative Study of Juvenile Delinquency in Pakistan

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Conflicts of Interest

Introduction

The act of committing a crime at a very young age is juvenile delinquency¹. A juvenile delinquent is

ABSTRACT

This article discusses the situation of juvenile justice in Pakistan and the need for a detailed, concrete and efficient strategy to resolve the juvenile justice problems. As such, at present there is no juvenile justice policy in the country. Juvenile Justice System Ordinance 2000 is the only significant statute dealing with children in dispute with the legislation. The law is not properly implemented in the country, due to some practical difficulties. Pakistan has many good policies, often on paper, such as health policy, education policy, labor policy, and so on, but at national or provincial level we have neither a criminal justice policy nor a clear juvenile justice policy.

This article discusses how the politics of criminal justice in Pakistan would look like. There is also discussion of all the legislation, legislation, statutes and rules that are binding on Pakistan defined by the national and international fora. The article further argues that although the courts have often issued contradictory judicial opinions, the increasing authority of the case law indicates a clear inclination of the courts to settle the matter, which is of great importance. This article discusses how the politics of criminal justice in Pakistan would look like. There is also discussion of all the legislation, legislation, statutes and rules that are binding on Pakistan defined by the national and international fora. The article further argues that although the courts have often issued contradictory judicial opinions, the increasing authority of the case law indicates a clear inclination of the courts to settle the matter, which is of great importance.

Keywords: JUVENILE JUSTICE, CRIMINAL JUSTICE, JUVENILE JUSTICE SYSTEM ORDINANCE 2000, JUVENILE DELINQUENCY, JUVENILE COURTS

¹ Farrington, D. P. (1992). Juvenile delinquency. *The school years*, 2, 123-163.

a young person who by committing a crime breaks a state or federal law, especially a teenager under the age of eighteen. Teens are still immatures and do not think like adults, so they are susceptible to making mistakes or committing crimes that are not completely in their power². Teens can violate laws for different purposes³, and there are a variety of causes that can lead them to juvenile delinquency⁴.

There are many schools of thoughts as to the primary factors that contribute to juvenile delinquency⁵. It is undoubtedly the case, though, that children who are abandoned, abusive or disadvantaged are statistically more likely to slip into a cycle of delinquency⁶. It is remembered that delinquent conduct is not limited solely to above-mentioned cases, adolescents with decent and loving parents, and acceptable living arrangements that also fall under delinquent behavior. Juvenile delinquency refers to any act that, if committed by an adult, may be a criminal offence. Juvenile delinquency is part of serious illegal conduct. Delinquency is an offense that can be considered a crime if committed by minors under the age of 18⁷, but the same action cannot be considered a crime if committed by an adult. At the time of commission, juvenile delinquency refers to the age specific to any illegal conduct⁸.

Children between the ages of 7 and 18 are responsible for the charge of their actions⁹. Children under the age of 7 as deemed by British law are not adequately capable of understanding between right and wrong¹⁰, so they do not have criminal intent. Juvenile is a child between 7 and 18 years of age and juvenile delinquency is the deviant conduct. Depending on their sensitivity to the essence of actions and criminal laws, various countries set the ages of the children as responsible for their delinquent acts. Young people are the society's main concern, their good conduct is very important for the smooth functioning of the community, which is why the sociologists and interested professionals have been researching their actions from very childhood¹¹. It is natural that not all individuals behave in the same manner, there are many variables that affect the behavior of individuals of all ages and eventually decide the social or asocial pattern of the behavior. Crime is an act that is considered contradictory to the current rules and regulations of society and the justice system has codified laws to prosecute and prevent the person responsible for his / her acts. Juvenile delinquency refers to actions committed by a young adult that has not reached adulthood, in breach of the Criminal Code. The term

² Black, C. (2020). *It will never happen to me: Growing up with addiction as youngsters, adolescents, and adults*. Central Recovery Press.

³ Flynn, D. (2012). All the Kids Are Doing It: The Unconstitutionality of Enforcing Statutory Rape Laws Against Children & Teenagers. *New Eng. L. Rev.*, 47, 681.

⁴ Patacchini, E., & Zenou, Y. (2012). Juvenile delinquency, E., and conformism. *The Journal of Law, Economics, & Organization*, 28(1), 1-31.

⁵ Boyden, J. (1997); Durkheim, Emile (1933); and Vold, George B. and Thomas J. Bernard (1986)

⁶ Miller, W. J. (2005). Adolescents on the edge: The sensual side of delinquency. *Edgework: The sociology of risk-taking*, 153-171.

⁷ Bortner, M. A. (1988). *Delinquency and justice: An age of crisis*. New York: McGraw-Hill.

⁸ Moffitt, T. E. (1990). Juvenile delinquency and attention deficit disorder: Boys' developmental trajectories from age 3 to age 15. *Child development*, 61(3), 893-910.

⁹ Cipriani, D. (2016). *Children's rights and the minimum age of criminal responsibility: a global perspective*. Routledge.

¹⁰ Platt, A., & Diamond, B. L. (1966). The origins of the right and wrong test of criminal responsibility and its subsequent development in the United States: An historical survey. *Calif. L. Rev.*, 54, 1227.

¹¹ Quennerstedt, A., & Quennerstedt, M. (2014). Researching children's rights in education: Sociology of childhood encountering educational theory. *British Journal of Sociology of Education*, 35(1), 115-132.

delinquent and recidivist act are important to understand, that delinquent is the official term or mark given to a person below the age who has diverged from community standards and is named as a specific act of delinquent act that breached the criminal code. Until a series of acts are likewise committed, a student who breaks the school window or clashes with other young people is not automatically branded as delinquent¹². Felony offences and status offenses are two major types of juvenile delinquency. If committed by a juvenile or an adult, acts such as violent assault, robbery, murder, arson, larceny, and associated substances are criminal and will be considered offences. These activities are the prime focus of the criminal justice system and timely steps are taken against them to prevent them. Although status offenses would not be pointed to as criminality if committed, for instance, by an adult leaving home, being away from home late at night, smoking cigarettes, and leaving the workplace early, if wanted to commit by a teenager, all the same acts would be considered an illegal act by nature.

British common law did not make children under the age of seven legally liable for criminal activities¹³, as it was assumed that children under the age of seven had no criminal intent⁶ required for conviction. Children below the 7 were considered not to have the understanding to differentiate between right and wrong. Neil Postman (1982) states that at the age of 7 and above the children had command of their speech which was also the explanation that seven were chosen as responsible age for the delinquent acts¹⁴. Legislation was enforced in Massachusetts in 1646¹⁵ for children who were deviant and deemed to be rebellious, since this law was under the jurisdiction of the colonists of the Puritans of America, making the children responsible for obeying the commands of their parents. Parents had to bring children to the courtroom to enforce on the children who disobeyed them the death penalty. Before the 17th century, children were dressed and treated as adults¹⁶, dancing with adults, engaging in sex and playing with private parts did not make them delinquent children, but later, especially in Europe, the social attitudes on children shifted and actions shifted so that children were treated differently from adults¹⁷. Children are now becoming the interest of the society, the moral and spiritual development of children has been given priority, the showing of private parts by children has been considered immoral, and guidance and oversight has been given to all children engaging in these deviant activities. Since the children under the age of 7 were deemed innocent and lacking criminal responsibility, the word adolescent came to be used for the children when the books were written in the mid-fifteenth century and children were taught to recognize their actions by Postman, 1982¹⁸. Postman, 1982, states

¹² Henning, K. (2004). Eroding confidentiality in delinquency proceedings: Should schools and public housing authorities be notified. *NYUL Rev.*, 79, 520.

¹³ Plucknett, T. F. T. (2001). *A concise history of the common law*. The Lawbook Exchange, Ltd..

¹⁴ Albrecht, R., Tabone, C., & Team, E. A. The Media Ecology of Play: Johan Huizinga, Neil Postman and a Pedagogical Response To the Challenges of Educating Children in the Digital Age.

¹⁵ Morris, R. B. (1926). Massachusetts and the Common Law: The Declaration of 1646. *The American Historical Review*, 31(3), 443-453.

¹⁶ Ariès, P. (1962). *Centuries of childhood* (p. 388). Harmondsworth: Penguin.

¹⁷ Gubernskaya, Z. (2010). Changing attitudes toward marriage and children in six countries. *Sociological Perspectives*, 53(2), 179-200.

¹⁸ Phelan, J. C., Link, B. G., & Tehranifar, P. (2010). Social conditions as fundamental causes of health inequalities: theory, evidence, and policy implications. *Journal of health and social behavior*, 51(1_suppl), S28-S40.

that social conditions encourage individuals during their lifespan to embrace the delinquency. If the juvenile was adversely influenced by friends, family members, school and justice departments, he or she may indulge in delinquency and this applies to the juvenile's interpersonal relationships with the above officials. Community ecological problems such as bad conditions in the inner city neighborhoods, different housing styles and disparities in class will contribute to delinquency for the person. Social shift that youth minds will be adversely impacted by global turmoil, economic instability, and governmental ill-decisions. In culture, social class will cause tension for people in mind, resulting in a lack of comprehension and discriminating between right and wrong. It is explained that criminology is to explore and clarify the 'social life trends.' It is a matter of finding out and examining the reasons of social behavior why specific social acts are taken by those people: criminal and non-criminal-whether human characteristics or environmental factors lead individuals to follow their preference or select alternatives for their course of action (Postman, 1988). The universe as an external influence influences people in behavioral settings¹⁹: social and social activity and it helps establish circumstances where people make decisions about their behaviors in cultural and institutional contexts. A juvenile delinquent who is usually under 18 may not be sentenced as an adult if he has committed a crime. Across the USA, however, multi-state laws reduce the level of criminal liability for violent offenses or repeat offenders to as small as 14 years²⁰.

Juvenile delinquency trend in Pakistan Juvenile delinquency is applied to comportment pursued by a youth not reaching maturity age in infringement of the criminal code²¹. The word "delinquent" and delinquent act is important to understand, that delinquent is the official term or label given to a person below the age who has deviated from community norms and is named as a specific act of delinquent act that violated the criminal code. Until a series of acts are likewise committed, a student who breaks the school window or clashes with other young people is not automatically branded as delinquent. There are broadly two types of juvenile delinquency: Felony offences and offenses of status. If committed by a juvenile or an adult, acts such as aggravated assault, robbery, murder, arson, larceny, and associated substances are criminal and will be considered offences. These activities are the prime focus of the criminal justice system and timely steps are taken against them to prevent them²². Although status violations would not be pointed to as criminality if committed, for example, by an adult running away from home, being away from home late at night, smoking cigarettes, and leaving the workplace early, if committed by a teenager, all the same acts would be considered criminal acts by nature. Kid and teen antisocial behavior is a criminal delinquency in Pakistan and elsewhere. Children and teenagers engaged in antisocial activity, for example, breach society's fundamental values,

¹⁹ Mason, W. A., Conrey, F. R., & Smith, E. R. (2007). Situating social influence processes: Dynamic, multidirectional flows of influence within social networks. *Personality and social psychology review*, 11(3), 279-300.

²⁰ Redding, R. E., & Shalf, S. M. (2001). The legal context of school violence: The effectiveness of federal, state, and local law enforcement efforts to reduce gun violence in schools. *Law & Policy*, 23(3), 297-343.

²¹ Talpur, F., Pathan, P. A., & Shah, P. (2012). Examining the causes of juvenile delinquency in Pakistan. *The Women-Annual Research Journal of Gender Studies*, 4.

²² Nisar, M., Ullah, S., Ali, M., & Alam, S. (2015). Juvenile delinquency: The Influence of family, peer and economic factors on juvenile delinquents. *Applied Science Reports*, 9(1), 37-48.

privileges, and rules; spreading lies is breaching the law, cheating is violating one's property rights, and running away from school is breaching the rule of school. A societal pattern of juvenile delinquency applies to conduct that breaks the statute. The problem of delinquency among children and teenagers and criminal tendencies in Pakistan has been caused by industrialization, rising urbanization and prevailing working-class conditions; social disparity, such as differing urban and rural growth rates, has arisen in society; unemployment rates; Under these circumstances, social reformists demanded the shifting position of the family, social structures, and governmental attention, and also called for urgent steps to resolve this distinctive social problem of the children's society. Khalid and Cheema's (2004)²³ study documented conflict among parents of children, and electronic media have a major impact on juvenile crime. The results of the 70 percent juveniles caught on murder charges by conducting research in the Faisalabad prison had complicated domestic life where parents had daily social and economic dispute.

SIGNIFICANCE OF STUDY:

Juvenile Delinquency and justice are a social problem for all nations, including the Pakistan. Skirmishes typically occur due to disproportionate levels of social class deprivation which is a push or pull cause of delinquency indulgence as children are strongly impacted by exposure to improper environments. The sobering predictions on the prospects of youth violence illustrate the need for solid, urgent, well-planned and decisive measures to intervene early in order to discourage younger children from adopting the self-destructive path of many of their older brothers and sisters. Around the same time, it is important that we respond adequately to the tiny number of young criminals who victimize the society repeatedly and account for the vast majority of serious and violent crime acts. To strengthen the ability of the criminal justice system to respond to juvenile offenders, we must take immediate action. If we do not respond to their wishes, the possible loss of human life and productivity to civilization would be a burdensome and tragic burden for future generations. The current thesis considers factors that influence juvenile delinquency and justice in Pakistan. This study is important because the concern for both Pakistani children and teenagers is greatly affected by socio-economic and psychological factors, particularly the age of seven to eighteen. This population is the possible future of our nation and they have to play an important part in the development of our country. Regrettably, some of these children and adolescents became offenders in their future lives due to insufficient socializing environment and other psychological factors that adversely affected their cognitive and psychological development.

The Government and localities have a range of options that are both important and challenging before taking action. Funds must be allocated for options for the juvenile justice program, ranging from safe facilities to day care, probation placements, and improvements in the collection of research and data and dissemination of information on issues related to juvenile violence. Support for a wide variety of innovative social

²³ Mahmood, K., & Cheema, M. A. (2004). Empirical analysis of juvenile crime in punjab, Pakistan. *Pakistan Journal of Life and Social Sciences*, 24, 10-9.

empowerment and crime reduction services, including after-school programs, childcare for low-income working mothers, neighborhood policing projects, summer recreation and low-income social career options, and Head Start, must also be made available.

In contrast to funding programs, there are several actions that can be taken by government and local communities to build on their responsibility to children's safety, health, development, and also well-being.

DISTINCT SYSTEM FOR JUVENILE JUSTICE NEEDED:

There is some importance that why do we need an autonomous criminal justice system? What do we need to have an impartial criminal justice system? There is a set of renowned criminologists who believe that a single comprehensive justice system is appropriate to deal with both juveniles and adults, and that a separate criminal justice system is not necessary.²⁴ Yet most juvenile justice participants argue in favor of a different program specifically dealing with youth.²⁵ The two corresponding articles make strong reasons for a separate criminal justice system. Social architecture of childhood has provided the source for the juvenile justice system²⁶, independent from the criminal justice system for adults (Jensen & Jorgen, 2006)²⁷. The creation of one or more exclusive juvenile courts in a section of the session, within three months of the launch of the JJSA, was another distinct feature of the Act. The JJSA was required by that exclusive court to rule on juvenile cases within six months of taking cognizance of the case; otherwise, the Juvenile Court will have to request an extension from the High Court concerned by explaining the reasons for not being able to decide the case within the time limit specified. If the Juvenile Court has not sought such an extension, the complainant or the juvenile may make an application in this respect to the High Court. At this stage (childhood / adolescence) the child's mental and physical skills have not developed themselves to an adult level. The child lacks the ability to fully grasp what he / she is doing, and the consequences of his / her actions (Junger-Tas, 2006)²⁸. Unlike parents, therefore, they cannot be held accountable for their actions. Based on this concept, kids in skirmish with the law need to be nurtured and guided to mature into accountable adults and they deserve an opportunity to correct their infringing activities (Jensen & Jorgen, 2006). It is among the reasons to put forward through international lawyers, criminologists and policy makers for a juveniles' comprehensive criminal justice program.

The diversion process was to be completed by the Juvenile Justice Committee as established by the JJSA's

²⁴ Modecki, K. L. (2020). Not Just Doing Time: Distinct Typologies of Attitudes and Emotions among Juvenile Justice-Involved Youth. *American Journal of Community Psychology*.

²⁵ De Anda, D. (2001). A qualitative evaluation of a mentor program for at-risk youth: The participants' perspective. *Child and Adolescent Social Work Journal*, 18(2), 97-117.

²⁶ Wiig, J. K., Tuell, J. A., & Heldman, J. K. (2013). Guidebook for juvenile justice and child welfare system coordination and integration. MA: Robert F. Kennedy Children's Action Corps.

²⁷ Jensen, E. L., & Jepsen, J. (Eds.). (2006). *Juvenile law violators, human rights, and the development of new juvenile justice systems*. Bloomsbury Publishing.

²⁸ Junger-Tas, J. (2006). Trends in international juvenile justice: What conclusions can be drawn?. In *International handbook of juvenile justice* (pp. 505-532). Springer, New York, NY.

2(j), and this Committee was to be created within three months of the Act 's beginning²⁹. The Committee is made up of the following members:

Judicial Magistrate Section, who shall also head the Committee; district public prosecutor; member of the local Bar having at least seven years standing at the Bar, appointed by the concerned Sessions Judge for a period of two years; and serving probation officer or social welfare officer not below the rank of an officer in BPS-17.

LEGAL FRAMEWORK OF JUVENILE DELINQUENCY

(a) International Laws and Conventions:

1. Convention 1990 about The Rights of the Child (CRC)
2. Children's Rights Convention (CRC) 1989
3. Minimum Guidelines of the United Nations for the administration of youthful justice 1980
4. Article 77 of the Geneva Conventions Additional Protocol-I 1977
5. Geneva Declaration on the Rights of the Child 1924
6. UN Instructions for the Defense of Youngsters Disadvantaged of their Freedom 1989

(b) National Law of Pakistan:

1. Juvenile Justice System Ordinance (JJSO) 2000
2. Code 1860 of Pakistan Penal
3. Crime of assault (implementation of) Order 1979
4. Criminal Method 1898 Code
5. Offender ordinance 1983 of Punjab Youthful
6. Act 1926 of Punjab Borstal
7. Sindh Children Act 1955
8. Sindh Borstal School Act 1955
9. Punjab Monitoring and Management of Children Homes, Act 1976 (The Punjab Poor and Abandoned Children Act, 2004)
10. The Reformatory Schools Act, 1897
11. Courts' power to order juvenile offenders to be sent to Reformatory Schools
12. Juvenile Smoking Ordinance, 1959
13. Probation of Offenders Ordinance 1960
14. Scope of the Ordinance of Probation of Offenders 1960
15. Service of Kids Act, 1991
16. The Children (Pledging of Labor) Act 1933 (applicable in all provinces)

²⁹ Iftikhar, K. (2019). Does a Juvenile Get a Better Law This Time-A Comparative Review of the New & Old Juvenile Laws of Pakistan. *LUMS LJ*, 6, 102.

17. The Employment of Children Act 1991 (applicable in Balochistan and ICT)
18. The Employment of Children Rules 1995 (applicable in Balochistan and ICT)
19. Khyber Pakhtunkhwa Prohibition of Employment of Children Act 2015
20. Punjab Prohibition of Child Labor at Brick Kilns Act 2016
21. Punjab Restriction on Employment of Children Act 2016
22. Sindh Prohibition of Employment of Children Act 2017

JUVENILE PRISONERS AND AVAILABILITY OF STATISTICS:

The idea of juvenile information is indivisible from 'un-openness.' The path that there are so various energetic condemned or condemned losers in Pakistani correctional facilities remains undefined due to a couple of segments' nonappearances of proper record-keeping, events including young liable gatherings being perceived as adults, and the social disfavor joined to the subject. This nonattendance of good record-keeping makes it hard to get explicit data while through the Right to Information Act (RTI). As demonstrated by real bits of knowledge given by the governing body of Punjab, there is a total of 599 juvenile prisoners of whom 529 are being endeavored and 70 are condemned. Grippingly, these 599 prisoners are male, and the organization doesn't exchange data on female juvenile miscreants or children living in prisons with their people.

There are presently 181 juvenile inmates in four provincial jails at Sindh. Of these children 168 are being charged and 13 are convicted. As in Punjab, data are not available on female juveniles detained in Sindh jails.

Juvenile Prisoners in Sindh

There are 338 youth reportedly offenders in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa. Of those 338, 311 are being tried while 27 are convicted. Data on female juvenile inmates in KP are not visible.

Juvenile Prisoners in KP

Talking with respect to Baluchistan, the official information shows that there are 70 adolescent detainees. Be that as it may, there are no figures accessible about the number of are being arraigned and the number of are being condemned.

Regardless, a JUI-F common legislator from Baluchistan, Sardar Abdul Khetiran, announced in October 2017 that there were 4,000 adolescent prisoners secured up different commonplace correctional facilities, and 99 percent of them are exposed to rape. When gotten some information about this colossal distinction in numbers—authoritatively recorded and cited by Khetiran—they didn't have any remark to make. In 2013, Pakistan's then Chief Justice took Suo Moto note of an investigation on adolescent detainees, as indicated by which 1500 adolescents were imprisoned in Pakistan in 2013, remembering 673 for Punjab; 262 in Sindh; 510 in the KPK and 55 in Baluchistan.

The graph shows a comparison of the data listed in a study published in 2013 and the latest available statistics. The number of juvenile inmates in Punjab, Sindh, and KPK has decreased by 74, 81, and 172, respectively, according to the graph, while in Baluchistan the number has increased by 15. Yet officials from all the provinces did not share any details about the difference that was achieved. Consequently, it is unknown if these children were sentenced, released or grown out of the juvenile system.

ABUSIVE BEHAVIOR IN JUVENILE'S JAILS:

The level of torture in police guardianship, a lot of which remains unreported, is staggeringly disturbing. A clinical gathering that met 200 children at the youthful current school in Karachi found that practically 60% of the youngsters were presented to authentic torture including over the top beating, electrical stager, giving (and) cheera (obliged broadening isolated from the hands, oftentimes in mix with kicks to the genitalia). "Raabia, eight, and her five-year-old sister were expressly assaulted after their mother was caught by police under Zina's charge, as demonstrated before sun-up 2004. All Perveen's five children were with her family, as her significant other was in like manner situated in jail under a holding onto offense. "I can at present feel those strong hands moving over my body scouring my privates, and that cruel male handle, giving me no craving for crying for help. The devil had my soul humiliated. There, it didn't end; rather he attacked my more energetic sister. She has cuts wherever on her body. There was none to support us, "Rabia included without language.

Regardless of this, practically all the staying 85,000 detainees (against a 31,000) work more awful than the creatures. Each prison in Pakistan is stuffed, and each detainee dozes on the dividers³⁰. Most individual prisoners are messed up and inappropriate behavior is regular. Latrines are soiled and arranged inside a similar cell, and are utilized by many detainees will in general experience the ill effects of scabies of skin illness.³¹

Conclusion

*Legislative reforms are not enough to shield children from all forms of abuse, bigotry, marginalization and the consequent juvenile delinquency.*³²

Pakistan is devoted to creating environments which will guarantee adolescents' healthy social life and reduce their risk of being exposed to divergent behavior. The government is making policies to free society from crime and juvenile delinquency especially. In the broad sense of children's social justice who are victims of an crime or derive into contact with the law, the state finds juvenile justice as an integral part of the justice. Implementing the holistic vision of social justice needs, in particular, a comprehensive criminal justice program and a general social program aimed at improving child safety and criminal welfare in order to reduce the need for structured judicial involvement. The Islamic Republic of Pakistan Constitution offers guidance on child security matters. Chapter one of the Pakistani Constitution (founding rights) applies specifically to protection of child.³³ The Article 25 of that constitution states that every people shall be equal to the law and shall have the right to equal treatment under the law.³⁴ There is no gender discernment. There is nothing in this Article shall prohibit the State to make any special provision to protect children and women. Under Article 35 of the Chapter two of the Constitution (policy's principles) states:³⁵ Marriage, marriage, mother and child shall be covered by the Government. The state is therefore regularly empowered to set up inclusive judicial and social systems to foster children's health and security and avert them from being vulnerable to juvenile delinquency. The numerous conventions and treaties have been already signed and ratified by Pakistan, like as the Convention on the Rights of the Child (CRC 1990) and the worst types of child labor (ILO Convention 2001). The Pakistan also ratified the CRC's 2nd optional protocol on child trafficking, child prostitution and child pornography. In parliament, the Bill for Improvement Criminal Law and the National Commission on the Protection of the Child have already been adopted as legislative measures, among others. The Criminal Law Reform Act introduces changes and insertions aimed at raising the least age to ascertain criminal

³⁰ Malik, W. A. (2019). The Juvenile Justice System and the Right to Dignity of Juvenile Offenders in Pakistan. *PLR*, 10, 141.

³¹ Riaz, N., & Amjad, S. (2019). The Status of Restorative Justice in Pakistani Legal System: An Analysis of Pakistani Laws With Special Reference to Certain Case Studies. *Restorative Justice in Pakistan*.

³² Need for a Juvenile Justice Policy in Pakistan by Sharafat A. Chaudhry & Dr Ejaz Hussain.

³³ Chapter 1, The Constitution of Pakistan 1973.

³⁴ Article 25, The Constitution of Pakistan 1973.

³⁵ Article 35, Chapter 2, The Constitution of Pakistan 1973.

liabilities, as-well-as criminalizing activities such as child pornography, sexual assault, human trafficking and cruelty. Likewise, setting up an independent and resourceful commission on children's rights, introduced in the National Commission on the Rights of the Child Act, would be a groundbreaking achievement in safeguarding children's rights. The last juvenile statute of (Juvenile Justice System Ordinance, 2000) was struck down by the Lahore High Court in 2004, which was found unconstitutional, unfair, and not practicable, and stated that a fresh statute should be enacted by the parliament to resolve the perceived ailments in Ordinance. Though, an appeal against that judgment is still in pending before the Supreme Court of Pakistan. Likewise, Pakistan's Law & Justice Commission and the Law Ministry, Justice & Human Rights embarked on a extensive and exasperating cycle of national consultations to examination the juvenile justice legal system from 2009. Accordingly, the 2015 Bill for Juvenile Justice System was introduced by the Ministry of Law & Justice along with Human Rights Ministry on the stakeholder's recommendations basis, but it has not yet been produced before the parliament. In latest conference, it had been addressed that a robust criminal justice framework for the successful application of the forthcoming legislation would be in place, along with the statute. Given the number of steps taken by Pakistan to guard children at risk and reduce the juvenile delinquency possibility, as there are number of children at-risk in country due to inadequate socio-economic indicators. The safety of children who are at-risk, protecting from juvenile delinquents and maintaining their fair place in the social system is undeniably a task that entails both individual and communal efforts. Legislative reforms are not enough to shield children from every sorts of abuses, bigotry, marginalization and the consequent juvenile delinquency. This also necessitates a comprehensive national criminal justice strategy focused on constitutional amendments. First of all, it is important to amend national legislation in the children's best interests by putting criminal justice system in line through constitutional criteria and global standards. The assessment of an accused's age is of great importance for resolving the juvenility argument. This can be achieved by establishing a systematic framework to ascertain an accused (or juvenile)'s age, outside the limits of a preliminary or subjective evaluation typically rendered by law officers.

The identification and founding of a criminal justice deviation program in Pakistan that prove to be a successful hallmark of proceedings of juvenile justice. There is essential need to establish strategies that will let children to be dealt with deprived of recourse to trials or formal court proceedings (like as diversion), where necessary and acceptable, if maximum consideration is given to human rights and legal protections. As a matter of juveniles' state-policy, instead of the prevalent adversarial and restrictive punishment system in the country so that the notion of restorative justice must be predictable and obligatory. The defendant must be provided with fundamental constitutional protections for criminal justice, like as the innocence presumption, the right of information of the proceedings, right to be remained silent, the right to representation, the right to cross examine witness, the right to the presence of parents or guardians and the right to appeal at tribunals. Non-discrimination values like gender sensitivity, protecting the child's interests, the right to life, security and growth and regard for the child's opinions should be accepted as an integral part of the criminal justice system.

Confined or detained must be treated as a final option. The confinement should be considered reformatory and for the infants, the social reintegration steps should be taken. The training programs for the officials consultation, concerned and coordination. The budgetary allocations for the study and advocacy and for implementing the reforms packages to be considered as an important feature of a potential juvenile policy.

Intervention is believed to be the best solution to avoiding juvenile delinquency in the beginning. It needs efforts from individual and organizational to keep away kids from illicit and unethical behaviors. Some concentrate on disciplinary deterrence needed to intimidate criminals by making it clear in their minds that if they break law they will get serious punishment and even explain the consequences of their offence. Implement the learning programs with incentives for income production, career advancement, and courses for vocational education that supports and discourage from associating with erroneous people. NGOs and the strong participation of local groups will also play crucial role to prevent youth crimes.

Preventive Programmes of Juvenile Delinquency:

The below two kinds of programmes helpful for preventing the juvenile delinquency:

(i) Individual Program:

Person services include crime prevention through rehabilitation, psychotherapy and professional education.

(ii) Environmental program:

The Environmental Strategy aims at improving the socio-economic factors that are presumably responsible for fostering crime. The following techniques, which are implemented in crime prevention programs, illustrate these two types of preventive approaches.

The system for juvenile justice is constructed on the juvenile justice policy's guiding principles in any country that represents a country's level of commitment to children's rights agreed on internationally. The agencies' uncoordinated and fruitless initiatives around juvenile justice can be turned into organized and fruit bearing actions by a clear strategy for all these stakeholders. The distribution of adequate funds, the formation of special juvenile courts, police units for juvenile, enhancement in conditions of prisons, training for probation officers, the formation of Borstal institutions, the creation of diversion services and informal restorative justice activities are some of the main issues of particular concern in Pakistan's youth justice policy. The CRC's ratification in the 1990s and nowadays it is time for the Pakistan to take meaningful measures toward the developing a sustainable and recognizable juvenile justice system, and to implement a robust, cost-effective and well thought out juvenile justice program.

RECOMMENDATIONS:

It is clear to conclude, with the aid of the results of the current study; further work is required to explain the affective, cognitive, and physiological mechanisms by which adolescents are attracted to antisocial behaviors. Complex growth pattern of behavior, taking into account environmental factors, needs to be further studied. Also, the nuances in different cultures should not be overlooked as a family atmosphere in America must be quite unlike in Pakistan's family culture. During this modern era of smartphones and hi-speed internet, teenagers are more likely to be influenced by outside home world. One significant argument relating to juvenile delinquency is to consider unexpected involuntary reactions in nuanced human behavior, as in this research, respondents with dangerous (murder) offenses were not found to be common offenders. Categorizing juvenile delinquents into habitual and non-usual offenders is expected in future study. Such categorizations can be useful in assessing the function of the family, and the related risk factors contribute to juvenile delinquency. In particular in cases where the deviant behavior of adolescents is documented, future work is required to examine the contrivances mediating the adolescents and the family relationships.³⁶

- a. Children awaiting prosecution or imprisonment have to face considerable challenges due to loopholes in regulations as well as the non-compliance or ineffective implementation of laws. The Commission is of the opinion that financial constraints that prevent the government from solving all the problems in one go, but it would be wrong to conclude that even small and moderate steps can not be taken in this regard. With the political will and genuine commitment to upholding the Convention's principles, a steady process of enforcement / implementation of the Convention can and must begin. Separate courts must decide juvenile cases but it is not possible to establish all these courts at once. This, of course, will temporarily raise the workload of these courts, but a steady increase in the number of judicial officers will ultimately solve the issue. Let a ambitious but incremental initiative be designed to establish independent juvenile courts to complete the cycle over the next 5 years. Similarly, preparation and action for the creation of juvenile facilities need to be undertaken. There are currently only two separate jail-cum-borstal juvenile institutions in the world, one at Bahawalpur (Punjab) and the other at Landhi (Sindh). A separate juvenile circle was formed at Peshawar Central Prison in the NWFP. Similarly, there is also a juvenile camp at Haripur Jail, located at Nathiagali. The sentenced juveniles are held separately in the Central Prison at Mach in Baluchistan. There has been no complete separation of the juveniles from the adult inmates elsewhere in the world. The climates as well as the conditions in areas where it is performed are far from satisfactory. It is so because portions of juveniles are produced inside jail precincts. International laws and domestic law concentrate on separating minors from adults, not only in jail but also in police / judicial custody, in order to shield underage offenders from violence and criminal interference. Therefore, the Government

³⁶ Riaz, N., & Amjad, S. (2019). The Status of Restorative Justice in Pakistani Legal System: An Analysis of Pakistani Laws With Special Reference to Certain Case Studies. *Restorative Justice in Pakistan*. North American Academic Research, 4(1) | 2021 | <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4437717> Monthly Journal by TWASP, USA | 52

must prepare a planned strategy to address this problem. To begin with, in all jails, provisions have to be made to isolate juveniles from adults. But segregation alone would not be enough; conditions must also be strengthened within these locations, making them conducive to their inmates' schooling, training, and rehabilitation. Similarly, plans should be made for the creation of suitable agencies and institutional structures to organize / manage the juvenile justice system. Proper orientation and training should be provided to workers at these facilities, sensitizing them to the unusual circumstances and special needs of juveniles. For all these workers who come into contact with juvenile offenders, proper preparation must be provided thus. This will include police staff, prosecutorial staff, prosecutors, correctional officers, probation officers, jail staff, and staff working in juvenile rehabilitation facilities, and others.

- b. As far as legal changes are concerned, the Government must explore the possibility of slowly implementing the 1983 Punjab Youthful Offenders Ordinance (hereinafter referred to as the Order). As the latest in the field, this law is relatively up-to-date, as it incorporates the current principles and ideas from contemporary jurisprudence, particularly in the area of criminal justice. With some slight changes and enhancements, this Law can be converted into a model code of juvenile justice. Such a code would have overarching effect vis-à-vis other legislation on the matter. Many provinces would follow it, and slowly introduce it. Nevertheless, with a view to further improving its provisions and harmonizing them with the Convention and other international instruments, it may incorporate the following amendments / additions in its text. The Pakistan Penal Code prescribes a maximum age of 7 years for the exemption from criminal liability. The Code extends the exception to 12 years, provided it can be shown to the court's satisfaction that the accused had not yet reached adequate maturity to recognize the essence and consequences of his actions on the occasion. In most Commonwealth jurisdictions, this pattern of setting two age limits, one subject to statutory presumption and the other reprehensible presumption, is practiced. These activity as minimum and maximum age limit varies as different states have imposed different ages, ranging from 6 to 18 years. For comparison, some jurisdictions do not enforce a minimum age requirement. There are several other countries where the question of criminal responsibility is determined not on the basis of any defined age limit, but on the basis of a review of the child's mental and psychological state / quality, and his role in the suspected crime commission. In these cases, the court makes an independent decision as to whether or not the child warrants being charged and prosecuted as an adult. Given the wide-ranging and varied practice and the divergent views / opinions on the merits and demerits of setting these minimum and maximum age limits, it is appropriate not to suggest any modification to the Pakistan Penal Code provisions. Instead, it may suggest a policy adjustment that will help improve the child's situation. It is also recommended that the new Code be granted overriding effect such that children are prosecuted by juvenile tribunals. Because of its aptitude, experience and expertise, the juvenile court will also be a more suitable venue for determining these matters and determining on the required course of action for

release or placement in a correctional facility in accordance with the child's age, mental capacity, character, etc.

- c. The Law prescribes a maximum limit of 15 years for entry into the juvenile justice system. The 1955 Sindh Children Act sets age limit at 16. The same has been accompanied by the proposed Child Offenders Bill 1995. Age levels are similar elsewhere in the country, with the maximum set at 21 years. There is also no standard international procedure on the topic of setting the maximum age limit for the benefit of the administration of juvenile justice. But the foreign instruments recommend a maximum limit of 18 years. Having examined the issue, the Commission takes the view that, for the time being, the age limit imposed by the 1955 Sindh Children Act, i.e. 16 years may be maintained and enforced universally throughout the country, and cases of children below that age limit may be tried solely by juvenile courts.
- d. Implementation of the Juvenile Justice Act will be strongly applied. Acting without the willing hands to enforce it is both ineffective and risky. Therefore, the government will ensure that the authorities are properly implementing the Act.
- e. Each Board of Juvenile Justice will collaborate with local child protection agencies to strengthen their effectiveness in providing safe shelters for abused and neglected children.
- f. Juvenile's case should not be referred to adult courts.
- g. All representatives serving in a board of juvenile justice or a juvenile court would be expected to have comprehensive and continuous training not only in the legislative and case law regulating delinquency but also in child growth, socio-cultural influences, family resources, the Board's relationship with and obligations towards social service organizations, and empirical findings on recovery intervention.
- h. To respond effectively and adequately, members of the Juvenile Justice Board will promote sufficient court services and Community programs.
- i. Ensuring and enhancing the efficiency of the juvenile protective care process will offer justice to juvenile who are in conflict with the law.
- j. The age referring to juvenile should not be reduced at all, because it would have far-reaching effects on India's criminal justice system, which would be harmful to the growth of justice and equality.

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